

These use cases are intended to assist researchers. The instructions in the text are not legally binding. If you have any questions about data protection, copyright, or other legal aspects, make sure to contact the relevant offices at your university.

The use cases were developed collaboratively by the open-science teams at the Basel and Bern University Libraries and the data-protection officer of the University of Basel following a workshop on data protection and the anonymization of qualitative research data. People involved: Silke Bellanger, Christina Besmer, Danielle Kaufmann, Iris Lindenmann, Jennifer Morger, Gero Schreier. [The German version of the use cases](#) was published on zenodo in 2022. In 2024, the use cases were translated into English by Anthony Mahler.

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Information Security

Use Case

An international research group is investigating the working conditions and processes in Asian textile factories. The group will conduct research on-site and interview employees and supervisors from various businesses. The project involves not only university employees but also auxiliary staff who are taking their private laptops to do field work. While in the field, they will rarely have access to a secure internet connection. Based on past research experiences abroad, the group knows that they have to plan on the possibility that computers could be examined or deleted during security checks when leaving certain countries. After the field research, the international research group will exchange their data internally.

How can the researchers ensure through suitable IT measures that information is not disclosed without authorization, that research data are not lost, and that the integrity of the data is safeguarded?

What needs to be arranged before you go abroad?

If you are working with sensitive data, it is strongly recommended that you contact the relevant IT departments and information-security officers at your university during the planning stage of the research project and seek advice. The principal investigators are responsible for IT security and must ensure, among other things, that anyone involved in the project who works with a private laptop also complies with the security requirements. IT departments can help with instructions and advice on encrypting data and computers. They can also provide advice on the specific data-security challenges of doing research abroad and international collaboration. You should also consider whether the governments of the countries you plan to do research in could have a political interest in the research and whether, for example, officials might try to install spyware on researchers' devices when they enter the country. If researchers might require IT sup-

port abroad, they should discuss this in advance with the IT departments and have the contact details of the IT departments with them.

What are suitable storage locations for research data while you are doing research abroad?

Local drives on personal computers, external hard drives, and USB sticks are not suitable as secure storage locations for research data. If unencrypted, the data on these storage media can be processed by third parties if they have access to them. This means that they can be read, altered, stolen, or deleted. Data should be stored on a secure university server or a suitable cloud as soon as possible after collection. For collaboration on international research projects, university IT departments can offer tips on secure cloud providers. Before using a cloud service, you need to check where and how it stores data and whether the service meets the necessary security standards.

[SWITCHdrive](#), for example, is recommended for collaborating with members of various Swiss universities. Sensitive data must always be encrypted for transfers and storage. Once data have been transferred to a secure server, they should be deleted from local hardware. You should make sure that the data are [securely deleted](#), that is, that they cannot be easily restored. IT departments can also provide advice on how to do this.

How must researchers transfer research data and share data with their project colleagues to be in compliance with data-protection laws?

At the start of a project, the project team should determine what research data will be circulated within the team. Research data must be anonymized or pseudonymized as soon as possible, and only anonymized or pseudonymized data should be shared within the project team. If possible, original research data should not be circulated; they should be encrypted or protected in another way and stored on a server. If data are pseudonymized, secure key management must ensure that the key for reidentifying the pseudonymized data is stored separately from the data and that strict authorization is required to access it. When data are processed in international project teams, the data-protection laws of the countries involved must be observed. In particular, when transferring data from Switzerland to other countries, researchers must ensure that the data are adequately protected by the applicable data-protection laws in the respective country. If a country has inadequate data protection, the project partners from that country must ensure that they comply with Swiss data-protection regulations by signing a contract before the data transfer. Conversely, it may be the case that the data-protection regulations in the countries of the project partners are stricter than the applicable laws in Switzerland. Then it is necessary to agree in a contract about how data protection will be appropriately guaranteed in Switzerland. The federal government has a [list](#) of countries whose data-protection laws are considered equivalent to those in Switzerland.

When conducting research in countries with insecure networks, regular visits to locations with a stable internet connection should be planned for data transfers. [SWITCHfilesender](#) can be used to transfer research data. Sensitive data should always be encrypted for transfers and storage.

What means of communication are suitable for communicating within the project group and with the study subjects?

For internal communication within a project team and for communication with study subjects, you must be careful to select a means of communication that guarantees data protection and so also ultimately the protection of the researchers and study subjects in case there are controversial topics. Facebook, WhatsApp, and the like are therefore not suitable means of communication in some contexts. For messenger functions, Threema and Signal, for example, are suitable. University IT departments can be contacted to find out which web-conferencing software they support and recommend.

In some countries, such as China, some communication apps that contain secure end-to-end encryption are blocked. Researchers should find out which services can be used before starting work on-site.

How should you handle handwritten notes?

In principle, one must also pay attention to data protection with handwritten notes. If they contain personal data, notes must be kept confidential and protected from being accessed by unauthorized persons. If there is a risk that research documents may be confiscated when you leave the country, then you should also digitize all personal or controversial analogue data and securely transfer them to a home server in advance. All handwritten notes that provide information about specific individuals must be destroyed. It is generally advisable to digitize all the data relevant to the research before leaving the country and to transfer them to a server that is backed up regularly. This will prevent the loss of data. One should note that SWITCHdrive does not create automatic back-ups.

What does that mean for this case?

While planning their project on textile factories, the researchers seek advice from the relevant departments at their university about exchanging data in collaborative international projects, data security abroad, and the security requirements of the participating universities. If the requirements of the individual universities and countries differ, they will adhere to the one with the strictest security standards.

At the start of the project, they have each university set up a hard drive for the project that is only accessible to the project members. They determine where the originals will be stored, what data they will share with each other in the research group, and how they will proceed. Before they leave, they ask the IT departments at their universities for advice, and they encrypt their computers. The IT departments set up the computers for the researchers and check that they have the latest patches and that all the security features are switched on. The principal investigators ensure that the private laptops also have this level of security if it is not possible to loan computers from the university. They also ensure that all the project members have access to their university's network and to the applicable project hard drive. If research is being conducted on private devices, the individuals using them have deleted all unneeded private data on them.

During their field research abroad, all the researchers and auxiliary staff save their private data and research data in separate directories. They watch out to formulate politically volatile information carefully, and they use their own abbreviations for interview partners rather than their real names. They regularly travel to a larger city and transfer the data in encrypted form to the servers of their home universities. After these transfers, they delete the data from their laptops. Before each departure from the country, they check that all the data have been deleted and overwritten.